

Call for papers

Applied Mathematics and Sciences: An International Journal (MathSJ) aims to publish original research papers and survey articles on all areas of pure mathematics, theoretical applied mathematics, mathematical physics, theoretical mechanics, probability and mathematical statistics, and theoretical biology. All articles are fully refereed and are judged by their contribution to advancing the state of the science of mathematics.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Abstract Algebra and Applications
- Adaptive control
- Agriculture, environment, health applications
- Algorithms
- Applications of modelling in science and engineering
- Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- Computational Complexity
- Computer modelling
- Control theory
- Differential Geometry
- Digital control
- Discrete Mathematics
- Embedded systems
- Evolutionary algorithms
- Fault detection and isolation
- Feedback control
- Functional Analysis
- Fuzzy logic and applications
- Fuzzy set theory
- Genetic Algorithms
- Genetic algorithms and evolutionary computing
- Graph Theory and Applications
- Hybrid systems
- Industry, military, space applications
- Linear and nonlinear control systems
- Linear and Nonlinear Programming
- Markov Chains and Applications
- Mathematical modelling
- Model predictive control
- Networked control systems
- Neural networks and fuzzy logic
- Neuro-Fuzzy Control
- Numerical Analysis
- Numerical analysis and scientific computing

- Operations Research
- Optimal Control
- Optimization and optimal control
- Optimization Theory
- Ordinary and Partial Differential Equations
- Process control and instrumentation
- Real and Complex Analysis
- Real-time issues
- Robust control
- Set Theory
- Sliding mode control
- Statistics
- Stochastic control and filtering
- Stochastic Modelling
- System identification and control
- Systems and automation
- Topology and Analysis

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: mathsj@airccse.org Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline: July 07, 2018**
- Notification: August 07, 2018
- Final Manuscript August 15, 2018
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

For other details please visit <http://airccse.com/mathsj/index.html>